

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MODELLING TECHNIQUES FOR IMPACT ON THICK FABRIC COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Despite the increased use of thick fabric Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) materials in highly loaded aerospace structures (e.g., 20-50mm thick CFRP structures), a comprehensive characterisation of damage due to impact events on these structures remains an elusive and challenging task. To address this issue, three methods with varying degrees of computational complexity are developed to simulate and predict a representative impact problem on a thick composite plate. These simulation methods range from a low-fidelity 1D semi-analytical impact response model to high-fidelity 2D and 3D numerical impact damage models. The accuracy, in terms of impact response and damage prediction, is assessed by comparison with experimental results. It was found that the higher fidelity does not directly translate to a higher accuracy due to challenging modelling strategies for the 2D and 3D numerical impact damage models. The 1D semi-analytical impact response model was found to be the most accurate in predicting the force and displacement histories of both large-mass and small-mass impact events. However, this model is not capable of predicting the extent of damage. Comparison of the resulting impact damage from the 2D and 3D numerical impact damage models with experiments showed that improvements are required to capture the correct damage mechanisms. These damage mechanisms are complex and increasing the model complexity requires an extensive evaluation of the modelling strategies and numerical variables. Improvements are suggested that should increase the accuracy of these models. Dynamics are important for thick laminates as there is almost no plate bending and most of the impact energy is absorbed in local damage and deformations. Thinner composites generally experience more bending and can therefore be evaluated quasi-statically.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recent developments in the aerospace sector have allowed for the use of Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) materials in highly-loaded aerospace structures, which results in thick structures (e.g., 20-50mm). CFRP materials are generally known for their high specific mechanical properties but simultaneously their low damage tolerance. Especially damage due to impact and the underlying damage mechanisms can be complex and therefore challenging to predict. Even more when using fabric material for their better impact damage resistance properties. In thick composite structures these damage mechanisms, the resulting damage, and the effect on the residual strength are not completely understood. Accurate numerical damage models might be able to quantify the damage resistance and clarify these damage mechanisms. In turn, these models could aid the design and certification process resulting in lower weight and lower cost composite structures. A challenge with numerical Finite Element Methods (FEM) is the trade-off between accuracy and efficiency.

The laminate response to impact in terms of force and displacement histories directly relates to the resulting damage [1, 2]. Analytical models to predict this response are already available [3], for example the models of Shivakumar et al. [4], Christoforou et al. [5, 6, 7], Olsson [8, 9], and more

recently Talagani [10], and Esrail and Kassapoglou [11]. Their methods include energy-balance models for peak force prediction, simple spring-mass models for determining the response over time, and more complex models requiring numerical solution techniques. For a more detailed analysis numerical models have been successfully employed for low-velocity impact by the team of Bouvet et al. [12, 13, 14] and Tan et al. [15]. Studies that focus on relatively thick composite structures are limited. Mittal [16] obtained a closed-form impact response solution that includes transverse shear, relevant for thick laminates. Zhou and Davies [17] studied the response of 10 and 25mm thick woven glass fibre laminates by low-velocity drop-tower experiments up to 1500J. Jackson and Poe [18] investigated the time histories of contact force and transverse shear on relatively thick laminates. Despite the mentioned studies, the impact response of thick composite structures has not been fully characterized due to the influence of a large number of relevant material and geometrical parameters.

This paper shows three methods that are able to solve an impact problem formulated in Section 2. Section 3.1 shows a low fidelity one-dimensional (1D) semi-analytical model, which is able to predict the impact response in terms of force and displacement histories relatively quickly. However, this model is not capable of predicting the extent of damage. Therefore, a medium fidelity two-dimensional (2D) numerical impact damage model is presented in Section 3.2 that is able to predict the impact response and resulting damage. To increase the fidelity and accuracy of this model a three-dimensional (3D) version is given in Section 3.3. By comparison with experimental results the accuracy of these models is assessed in Section 4. In addition the advantages and limitations of each of these models are qualitatively compared. Section 5 elaborates on the conclusions and future work.

2 IMPACT PROBLEM

In order to carry out a comparative analysis of various analysis methods, a plate problem is chosen as representative of a thick aerospace composite structure under impact loading. The goal is to simulate impact experiments with a rigid spherical 16mm diameter impactor on a 150x100mm rectangular plate along the out-of-plane direction. The specimen is supported according to the ASTM D7136 standard for drop-tower impact. The supporting frame has a 125x75mm rectangular opening and four clamps are located 12.5mm from each corner of the specimen, see Figure 1. A large-mass (e.g., tool drop) and a small-mass (e.g., runway debris) impact case are considered.

Figure 1: Illustration of the 3D impact problem with the 2D approximation as a cross-section in the xz -plane through the plate centre and 1D approximation at the plate centre along the z -axis.

Experimental results of the impact problem are readily available. An extensive experimental study for 55J and 100J large-mass (drop-tower) and small-mass (impact-gun) impacts on 20mm and 40mm thick specimens with multiple layups has been performed at the Royal Netherlands Aerospace Centre (NLR). The experiments are simulated using three distinct models with varying types of approximations. The first model is a one-dimensional (1D) approximation in terms of a semi-analytical impact response model that can provide a prediction for the response properties along the z -axis at the plate centre. One level higher is a two-dimensional (2D) approximation model represented as a cross-section in the xz -plane (long dimension) through the plate centre. Finally, a fully three-dimensional (3D) model is used to simulate the same experiment. The accuracy of the models

presented in Section 3 will be assessed by comparison with some of these experimental results. Since the cross section cuts of the specimens have not been performed at the time of writing this paper, the internal damage will be instead compared with similar experiments, for which cross sections are available, which should have qualitatively the same damage patterns due to impact.

3 SIMULATION METHODS

3.1 1D Semi-Analytical Impact Response Model

One analytical impact response model that has proven quite capable of providing meaningful predictions over a whole range of impact types is the model of Christoforou and Yigit [6]. They assumed that a simply supported plate centre deflection (w_p) is described by a series expansion with an unknown amplitude (q_{mn}) as in Equation 1, where for centrally loaded plates s_{mn} is described by Equation 2, that is,

$$w_p = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} q_{mn} s_{mn} \quad (1)$$

$$s_{mn} = \sin \frac{m\pi}{2} \sin \frac{n\pi}{2} \quad (2)$$

To apply this model to the impact problem it is assumed that the plate is simply-supported instead of the boundary conditions illustrated in Figure 1. Whitney and Pagano developed plate equations of motion that include transverse shear stresses [19], which are more dominant in thick composites due to the lack of bending. A special orthotropic form ($A_{16} = A_{26} = B_{ij} = D_{16} = D_{26} = 0$) was developed by Dobyns [20]. Inserting Equation 1 into these orthotropic plate equations of motion gives the following system of second-order Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs):

$$\frac{d^2 q_{mn}}{dt^2} + \omega_{mn}^2 q_{mn} = \frac{4F}{m_p} s_{mn} \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{d^2 q_{mn}}{dt^2} s_{mn} \right) + \frac{d^2 \delta}{dt^2} = -\frac{F}{m_i} \quad (4)$$

The natural frequencies (ω_{mn}^2) of a simply-supported composite laminate are determined using the method of Christoforou and Swanson [5]. The equation of motion of the impactor in Equation 4 results from using Newton's Second Law (i.e., $m_i \ddot{w}_i = -F$), the fact that indentation (δ) is plate deflection minus impactor displacement (w_i), and Equation 1. In the above equations m_p and m_i are the plate and impactor mass. The system of $m \times n + 1$ second-order ODEs has to be reduced to the first order by introducing the following set of variables: $q_{mn,1} = q_{mn}$, $q_{mn,2} = q'_{mn}$, $\delta_1 = \delta$, and $\delta_2 = \delta'$. This results in a $2 \times m \times n + 2$ system of first-order ODEs, that is,

$$\begin{aligned} q'_{mn,1} &= q_{mn,2} \\ q'_{mn,2} &= \frac{4F(\delta_1)}{m_p} s_{mn} \delta_1^q - \omega_{mn}^2 q_{mn,1} \\ \delta'_1 &= \delta_2 \\ \delta'_2 &= -\frac{F(\delta_1)}{m_i} - \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{d^2 q_{mn}}{dt^2} s_{mn} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

In terms of initial conditions it is assumed that the initial rate of indentation (δ_2) is equal to the initial impactor velocity ($v_{i,0}$) and all other variables are zero. The contact force is a function of the indentation described by a contact law. There are several contact laws available, but not all are valid for thick composite impact where large indentations and high forces are present. A simple Hertz contact law is not valid for these large indentations for example [8, 10]. A more appropriate model has been proposed by Talagani [10]. The contact formulation is divided into three stages: elastic Hertzian loading, elastic-plastic loading as proposed by Yigit and Christoforou [21], and unloading as proposed by Yang and Sun [22].

$$F(\delta) = \begin{cases} k_\alpha \delta^{3/2} & \text{for } 0 \leq \delta < \delta_y \\ k_y(\delta - \delta_y) + k_\alpha \delta_y^{3/2} & \text{for } \delta_y \leq \delta \leq \delta_m \\ F_m \left(\frac{\delta - \delta_0}{\delta_m - \delta_0} \right)^{5/2} & \text{for } \delta_m < \delta < \delta_0 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

For the unloading F_m and δ_m are the maximum force and indentation prior to unloading. The critical indentation (δ_y) is a material dependent parameter and assumed equal to 0.3048mm as used by Talagani [10]. The permanent indentation after impact (δ_0) is determined by Equation 7. The Hertzian contact stiffness (k_α) and elastic-plastic contact stiffness (k_y) are given by Equations 8 and 9 [6].

$$\delta_0 = \delta_m \left[1 - \left(\frac{\delta_y}{\delta_m} \right)^{5/2} \right] \quad (7)$$

$$k_\alpha = \frac{4E_z \sqrt{R_i}}{3(1-\nu_{rz}\nu_{zr})} \quad (8)$$

$$k_y = \frac{3}{2} k_\alpha \sqrt{\delta_y} \quad (9)$$

In the previous relations, it is assumed that the impactor stiffness is significantly larger than the laminate through-thickness stiffness (E_z) such that the impactor can be modelled as rigid. The system of first-order ODEs described in Equation 5 above is solved using *ode45* in Matlab¹. As a result the indentation $\delta(t)$ and $q_{mn}(t)$ histories are obtained. The force history $F(t)$ is subsequently obtained using Equation 6 and the plate deflection history $w_p(t)$ is obtained from Equation 1. The impactor velocity $v_i(t)$ and displacement $w_i(t)$ histories are calculated by integrating the impactor acceleration derived from the force. In Section 4 the 1D semi-analytical impact response model results will be shown and evaluated.

3.2 2D Numerical Impact Damage Model

Although the 1D semi-analytical impact response model presented in Section 3.1 gives an indication of the response, it provides no information related to the extent of damage. There are methods available that can determine the 3D stress state from the force history and subsequently determine the internal damage using failure criteria [11]. However, a numerical FEM model has the potential to give a very accurate description of the damage. In addition, it is possible to correctly represent the boundary conditions mentioned Section 2 instead of assuming simply-supported boundary conditions. A first step in this direction is a 2D numerical impact damage model developed in Abaqus/Explicit. An explicit solver is preferred as the total impact duration is in the order of 0.1-1.0ms, which imposes a stricter requirement in terms time step size compared to the stable time increment condition.

Figure 2: Illustration of the 2D numerical impact damage model with the support edges at the bottom, clamps represented by a spring damper system at the top edges, and the rigid impactor in the top middle. A detailed illustration of the mesh with zero thickness cohesive elements in red is given on the right. Note that this figure corresponds to the cross-section along the xz -plane in Figure 1.

¹ *ode45* solves non-stiff differential equations based on a variable step Runge-Kutta method.

The spring damper systems representing the clamps have a spring stiffness of 1MN/m, which is critically damped and loaded at 1kN. Hard rough contact is assumed as interaction between the clamp and top ply. Hard frictionless contact is defined for contact of the impactor and support with the laminate. In terms of damage there are multiple numerical methodologies available in literature [2]. In the present work, cohesive interface elements (COH2D4) are used to model delaminations as well as intra-ply fracture, similar to the work of Bouvet et al. [12, 13, 14]. The behaviour of the cohesive elements is described by a traction-separation law using a linear damage evolution with a Benzeggagh-Kenane energy based mode-mixity formulation [23]. As we are working in Abaqus/Explicit, a mass matrix is defined and as such the cohesive elements should have a non-zero mass while ideally the cohesive elements have no mass. The mass can be reduced by decreasing the section thickness or cohesive density (ρ_c). In addition, the cohesive stiffness (K_c) should be sufficiently high to not reflect the stress waves due to impact. However, the stable time increment (i.e., inverse relation with computational time) decreases significantly for a high cohesive stiffness and low cohesive density by a factor $\sqrt{\rho_c/K_c}$. After an analysis of the effect of cohesive elements on stress waves, it was concluded that a cohesive stiffness of 1e16N/m and a cohesive density a factor 1e6 lower than the bulk material density are sufficient while keeping the stable time increment relatively low.

In terms of other modelling options, a case study was conducted. For example, one can model the cross section along the long or short in-plane dimension of the specimen. Also, representing the specimen as in Figure 2, the 2D state is neither plane stress nor plane strain. In the present case study plane strain (CPE4R) and plane stress (CPS4R) elements were studied. An additional limitation of the 2D impact damage model is the incorrect representation of the boundary conditions. It is not possible to match the supporting frame on all four edges of the specimen. Therefore, the 2D numerical impact damage model will represent plate curving (i.e., bending) in one direction instead of two directions. As a result, the plate bending may be too high compared to the experiments. To address this in the case study, a closed support preventing plate bending was added as an opposing extreme case. The model with a cross-section along the long in-plane dimension, CPS4R elements, and an open support was found to be the closest to the force/displacement histories of experiments. In Section 4 the 2D numerical impact damage model results will be shown and evaluated.

3.3 3D Numerical Impact Damage Model

Due to the limitations of the 2D numerical damage model in the previous section, a full scale model as illustrated in Figure 1 is needed to capture the behaviour of the impact with a minimum number of modelling assumptions. Modelling impact damage in 2D is restricted due to the missing interaction in the third dimension of all the damage mechanism as well as other numerical limitations such as contact definitions. In addition, for the 2D model plane strain is assumed but in reality neither the plane strain nor plane stress assumptions hold.

Figure 3: Illustration of the 3D ply aligned mesh in the xy-plane for (a) the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies and (b) $0/90^\circ$ plies. The edges that contain in-ply cohesive elements are highlighted in red.

Figure 4: Impact response comparison for a 55J large-mass (2274g) impact on a 20mm thick 150x100mm plate comparing (a) the force and (b) the impactor displacement history.

The 3D numerical impact damage model uses a similar methodology compared to the 2D numerical impact damage model. Again cohesive elements (COH3D8) are used to allow in-plane fracture and delaminations between plies with the same cohesive behaviour as discussed in Section 3.2 except that the cohesive stiffness is reduced to $1e14$ N/m to keep the computational time manageable. In addition, a ply aligned mesh allows for fracture perpendicular to the warp and weft direction of the fabric material. General contact is applied which enables the use of cohesive element deletion. For normal contact, the pressure-overclosure is enforced by using a scale factor with a contact stiffness scale factor of 2.0 and an overclosure factor of $1/125^{\text{th}}$ of the ply thickness. These values result from a two element contact optimisation with the goal to minimise the overclosure between the elements for a reasonable increase in computational time. Frictionless tangential behaviour is used except for contact between the clamps for which a rough formulation is used. The bulk material is modelled using hex (C3D8R) elements for the 0° and 90° plies and wedge (C3D6R) elements for the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies. A scaled version of the ply aligned mesh is illustrated in Figure 3. In addition to the in-ply cohesive elements, this method allows for the use of cohesive elements between the plies as the nodes are aligned. Cohesive elements that are located outside the free opening of the support frame are deleted as no damage is expected in these regions. The bulk elements are scaled with a factor in the in-plane direction in order to keep the number of degrees of freedom manageable.

4 COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

The impact problem mentioned in Section 2 has been evaluated by all three models presented in the previous section and are compared with experimental results. The impact response comparison is discussed in Section 4.1 for large-mass (Figure 4) and small-mass (Figure 5). A comparison of the impact damage as predicted by the 2D and 3D numerical impact damage models is given in Section 4.2. The computational time in relation to the model accuracy is reviewed in Section 4.3. Material properties are available from extensive coupon testing campaigns and are not calibrated.

4.1 Impact Response

From Figure 4 and 5 it is observed that the 1D semi-analytical impact response model is best in line with the experiments in terms of force and displacement histories. Despite the simply-supported assumption the response is captured accurately which indicates that the local response is dominant in these types of impact. Nevertheless, with this model detailed damage cannot be predicted. The waviness in the experimental force response in Figure 4a is due to impactor natural frequencies which is not included in the model. A common assumption is often that increasing the fidelity (read complexity) of a model increases the accuracy of the required result. However, as discussed in Section 3 there are many modelling parameters and numerical variables that will affect the result. The current

iterations of the 2D and 3D numerical impact model are able to give some indication of the response and the differences with experiments are discussed below.

It can be seen that the 2D numerical impact damage model over predicts the force history and under predicts the impactor displacement history. This is a result of a significantly lower predicted indentation at the impact location. An improvement of the model should be able to model crushing of the first few plies to form an impact crater (e.g., Figure 6). Due to the lack of general contact it is not possible to delete fully damaged cohesive elements as the contact definitions are lost in that case. This limitation is especially evident for a small-mass impact (Figure 5) where for the experiments a large portion of the energy goes into indentation damage. In addition to this limitation the effects of the inaccurate boundary conditions and plane stress assumption are hard to assess.

Figure 5: Impact response comparison for a 55J small-mass (16.72g) impact on a 20mm thick 150x100mm plate comparing (a) the force and (b) the impactor displacement history.

The two limitations for the 2D numerical impact damage model mentioned above do not apply for the 3D numerical impact damage model. The force history is under predicted for the large-mass impact but quite accurate for the small-mass impact. Unfortunately, the predicted impactor displacement is too high. One possible explanation is that, due to the high forces at the impact location, the cohesive element deletion causes the bulk elements to distort significantly. In addition, the laminate is too compliant due to the lowered cohesive stiffness resulting in a larger plate deflection.

Figure 6: Illustration of an impact crater due to a 55J small-mass (16.72g) impact on a 20mm thick 150x100m plate. Note that this type of damage corresponds to the response in Figure 5.

(a) 2D numerical impact damage model prediction.

(b) Visual inspection of an impacted cross-section.

Figure 7: Comparison of the 2D impact damage model damage pattern (a) with a 50J large-mass (2268g) impact on a 15mm thick 140x100mm specimen performed at NLR (b).

4.2 Impact Damage

First, the accuracy of the 2D numerical impact damage model is assessed by comparison with experiments performed at NLR and Fokker Landing Gear (FLG). These experiments slightly differ in terms of specimen dimension and impact mass and energy compared the impact problem illustrated in Section 2. As mentioned in Section 4.1 the plate deflection of the 2D numerical impact damage model is too high for large-mass impact. Therefore it was decided to predict the impact damage with a closed frame preventing bending of the specimen. For small-mass impact this is not required as the damage mainly results from stress waves and vibrations of the plate.

For the large-mass low-velocity case an acceptable agreement is found as shown in Figure 7. The model is able to predict transverse cracks and delaminations due transverse shear stresses in a butterfly shape with a reasonable prediction in terms of the width and depth. Note that the damage is only in the cohesive elements, no damage is accounted for in the bulk material. Figure 8 shows a comparison of internal damage due to a small-mass high-velocity impact event. Most of the damage at the impact location is represented and delaminations extend through all plies. The area below the impact location shows no damage and fibre breakage occurs at the bottom ply. However, there is too much influence of the supports on the bottom left and right due to a high stress concentration which not present in the experiments.

(a) 2D numerical impact damage model prediction.

(b) Visual inspection of an impacted cross-section.

Figure 8: Comparison of the 2D numerical impact damage model (a) with a 140J small-mass (27.5g) impact on a 20mm thick 190x100mm specimen performed at FLG (b) [24]. Note that only the damage is shown, the layup has been removed for reasons of confidentiality.

(a) C-scan delamination area.

(b) 3D numerical impact damage model top view.

(c) 3D numerical impact damage model cross-section.

(d) 2D numerical impact damage model.

Figure 9: Impact damage comparison for a 55J large-mass (2274) impact on a 20mm thick 150x100mm plate for the predictions of the 3D numerical impact damage model with (b) a top view and (c) a cross-section view and (d) 2D numerical impact damage model to (a) experimental results.

As will be discussed in Section 4.3 the 3D numerical impact damage model has a significant computation time and therefore the impact events of Figure 7 and 8 have not been evaluated yet. Nevertheless, the impact cases corresponding to Figure 4 and 5 have been evaluated and can be compared. The experimental result is averaged over four specimens. For conciseness, only one representative specimen is shown in Figure 9a and 10a. Figure 9 shows the damage comparison of the large-mass impact event. The average experimental delamination dimensions are 26.75x25.50mm (514mm²) with a depth of 5.13mm. From Figure 9b and 9c it is clear that the 3D numerical impact damage model significantly over predicts the damage, the predicted dimensions are 44.97x41.50mm (1453mm²) with a depth through the full specimen. This over prediction of damage also relates to the lower predicted force and higher impactor displacements. It was observed that the stress wave travels through the whole specimen causing damage through the full thickness. Improvements are required to correctly capture these stress waves. In contrast to the 3D numerical impact damage model, the 2D numerical impact damage under predicts the damage, which also directly relates to the prediction of the impact response. From Figure 9d it is observed that the damage depth is predicted quite accurately (i.e., 4.6mm) but the predicted delamination width is just 8.8mm.

In Figure 10 the same comparison is given for a small-mass impact. The average experimental delamination dimensions are 36.00x33.50mm (892mm²) with a depth of 6.63mm. The predicted delamination width and height of 44.97x47.17mm (1602mm²) of the 3D numerical impact damage model are closer to the experiment compared to the large-mass impact case. However, the damage still extends through the full thickness of the specimen. The predicted damage pattern in Figure 10d using the 2D numerical impact damage model is quite complex. As mentioned above, stress waves play a significant role for small-mass impact. One limitation in terms of interpreting the results is that the stress waves are not captured accurately. The damages on the left and right side of the specimen are a direct result of reflecting tension waves from the specimen boundaries. If these damages are neglected, the predicted width is still too large (i.e., 46mm). In addition, the bottom part of damage below the impact location is due to these reflecting waves.

Figure 10: Impact damage comparison for a 55J small-mass (16.72g) impact on a 20mm thick 150x100mm plate for the predictions of the 3D numerical impact damage model with (b) a top view and (c) a cross-section view and (d) 2D numerical impact damage model to (a) experimental results.

4.3 Computational Time

The 1D semi-analytical impact response model is able to solve a small-mass impact problem in approximately 10 seconds and a large-mass impact problem in approximately 100 seconds due to the increase in impact duration. This computational time is orders of magnitude lower than the numerical impact damage models. For example, the 2D impact response model has about 250,000 Degrees of Freedom (DOF) and took about 2,000 seconds for small-mass impact and 14,000 seconds for large-mass impact, both on 8 cores. As expected the computational time of the 3D numerical impact damage model with about 14 million DOF is even higher, for example in the order of 80,000 seconds on 16 cores for small-mass impact and about 330,000 seconds on 48 cores for large-mass impact. The justification of these high computation times depend on the use case and required accuracy. While the accuracy of the numerical impact damage models is not sufficient, the future implementations of these models (as discussed in the Section 5) are expected to provide predictions with improved accuracy.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Three simulation methods have been presented to solve an impact problem on thick fabric composite structures. First, a low-fidelity 1D semi-analytical impact response model was presented that used the model of Christoforou and Yigit [6] in combination with the Sun-Christoforou contact model proposed by Talagani [10]. The 2D numerical impact damage model represents the specimen as a cross-section along the long dimension (xz-plane). Cohesive elements are used to model delaminations between the plies and intra-ply fracture. There are several limitations of the 2D numerical impact damage model. Because general contact is not available, it is not possible to delete cohesive elements to include the ply crushing damage mechanism. The assumed 2D state is neither plane stress nor plane strain and the boundary conditions are limited. This modelling strategy has a significant influence on the plate dynamics and resulting damage. However, the 2D impact damage model can give relatively fast results, which can be used for generating basic trends useful in design.

In order to mitigate these limitations a 3D numerical impact damage model with a ply aligned mesh was proposed. In theory this model gives the most accurate representation of the impact problem but at the cost of a significant increase in computational time.

The accuracy of these methods was assessed by comparing the predicted impact response and predicted damage with experimental results. In terms of impact response the prediction of the 1D semi-analytical impact response model is most accurate while also being several orders of magnitude faster than the numerical impact damage models. However, this model gives no indication of the extent of damage. The 2D and 3D numerical impact damage models can give an indication of the resulting impact damage. However, these models are only accurate in some cases. Improvements are required to increase the accuracy. The first improvement is currently in development which should give the 2D numerical impact damage model the ability to capture the ply crushing damage mechanism. In addition, for both the 2D and 3D numerical impact damage models improvements are required to accurately capture the stress waves. In the experiments we assume that the stress waves reflect from interfaces between yarns and resin rich areas. Due to this the stress waves lose magnitude much faster than is currently included in the models.

It can be concluded that impact on thick composite structures is a complex problem to solve. Dynamics are important as there is almost no plate bending and most of the impact energy is absorbed in local damage and deformations. Thinner composite structures generally experience more bending and can therefore be evaluated quasi-statically.

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